

AIART: ADVANCING THE REALM OF ART WITH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract. As Artificial Intelligence (AI) continues to advance and find applications in various industries, an increasing number of artists are delving into the potential possibilities of AI in the realm of art. They are incorporating cutting-edge techniques like neural networks and deep learning to explore a new genre of art known as Artificial Intelligence Art (AiArt). AiArt is a collaborative creative process that combines artists, technical experts, intelligent robots, and audiences, utilizing AI as the central medium for expressing thoughts and emotions. This article aims to define AiArt as a distinct art form, offering inspiration and guidance to art practitioners, theorists, and scientists, particularly in the context of "artificial intelligence injected artistic creation" discussed at the conference. The paper provides a brief overview of recent developments in AiArt, followed by an analysis of the essence and characteristics of this emerging art form, drawing from the underlying disciplines of AI artworks. Ultimately, the study concludes that the nature of AiArt lies in its diversification of subjects, the intelligence of the medium, and the modernization of expression, setting it apart from traditional forms such as painting, sculpture, and digital art. Additionally, the paper introduces four new features specific to AiArt: synesthetic experiences, fluidity and adaptability, interaction and communication, and permeation and integration.

Keywords. Artificial intelligence (AI); art; artificial intelligence art (AiArt); essence of AiArt; characteristics of AiArt.

Introduction

It is widely recognized that the relationship between art and science and technology is intricate, enduring, and constantly evolving. As new technologies emerge, some artists gradually abandon their traditional tools in favor of utilizing the latest inventions as alternative mediums. This shift has significant impacts on the production of art and the way it is perceived by viewers [1]. Just as the inventions of pigments, the printing press, photography, and computers revolutionized art, it is believed that AI is the latest technological revolution that will profoundly transform the artistic process and expand our creative potential and imagination [2].

AI is a field of computer science dedicated to exploring the capabilities and methodologies of using digital computers to simulate and extend functions performed by the human brain, such as sensory perception, language comprehension, and complex problem-solving [2]. With the advancements in big data and cloud computing over the past two decades, AI has made significant breakthroughs in key technologies like machine learning, natural language processing, speech recognition, and computer vision. Artists have keenly recognized the potential applications of AI in the field of art [6], eagerly embracing AI as a medium for artistic creation. This convergence of AI and art has given birth to a new art form called AiArt, which possesses distinct artistic standards and features that require further research and redefinition.

However, theoretical research on AiArt has lagged behind its practical implementation. There are few studies that delve into the ideological and

theoretical aspects of AiArt, with most papers focusing on technical aspects and applications. In 1983, digital artist Stephen Wilson [1] anticipated that developments in AI could enable artworks created by artists to learn from experience and interact with audiences in intelligent ways, akin to human sensibilities. He emphasized the importance of AI for visual artists, encouraging their active participation in this inevitable trend. AI expert Kaifu Li published a monograph titled "Artificial Intelligence" in 2017, discussing the relationship between AI and artistic creation [8]. He argued that AI-based artistic processes merely imitate specific creative styles by learning from a vast database of human works. As a result, computers are unlikely to approach or surpass human artists in the near future. Renowned artist Liqing Tan provided a bold interpretation and prediction for the future development of AiArt, introducing the concept of singularity art [9]. He examined the challenges artists will face with the advent of strong AI and analyzed the nature and characteristics of singularity art, along with the novel relationship between artists and the audience. Tan proposed that singularity art represents a fusion of human intelligence and AI when science and technology reach the singularity point. Singularity artists transcend their roles as mere creators and messengers, becoming participants and coordinators, while viewers transform into participants and creators. The boundaries between viewers and creators become blurred.

There is a widespread belief that the utilization of AI as a central medium by artists to create increasingly intelligent artworks has thrived. The emergence of captivating artistic robots has showcased their remarkable ability to imitate [11]. However, there remains a pressing need to understand the true nature and

characteristics of AiArt. What exactly is AiArt, and what are its principles and prospects? These questions require urgent theoretical exploration to prevent the blind development of AiArt practice. Consequently, this article aims to provide theoretical insights into the essence of AiArt and identify its distinctive features that set it apart from other art forms.

The first stage

The period from the 1960s until the late 20th century marks the initial phase of AiArt, specifically known as computer art. As AI falls under the domain of computer science, computer art serves as the precursor and foundation for AiArt. During this stage, numerous foreign artists and art enthusiasts began generating artworks with the assistance of digital computer programs. They would first conceive the desired visual art patterns in their minds and then proceed to write program code to achieve the intended renderings and drawings with mathematical features. In the early 1960s, Desmond Hen, a lecturer at the University of Manchester, utilized a bomb simulation computer program from World War II to develop the world's earliest automatic drawing machines known as the Henry drawing machine [1]. In 1963, the American computer magazine "Computer and Automation" organized the inaugural computer image competition, sparking a frenzy of computer image creation. Harold Cohen, an art professor at the University of California, San Diego, was among the earliest pioneers of computer art. He created the AARON computer program, which produced a series of regular images [2]. Figure 1 illustrates the process of artwork creation using AARON.

Figure 1. The process of creating artwork by AARON

Conclusion

Since the mention of AI at the Dartmouth conference in 1956, its technology and scope have continuously evolved with the advancements of the times. In today's era, AI has acquired new significance, driven by the advancements in big data and deep learning, reigniting its potential. Art, on the other hand, has been undergoing a continuous integration process with technology. The combination of AI and art has traversed several stages of development. Only in recent years has it begun to gain attention from the audience, with AiArt exhibiting an explosive growth trend accompanied by various art exhibitions and competitions. However, theoretical discourse on AiArt has lagged behind the practice of creation, with limited availability of theoretical journals and discussions dedicated to the art of AI. This research area remains relatively young. Consequently, a deeper understanding of the interaction between AI and art, as well as their mutual influence and support, is crucial. To address this gap, we have conducted a preliminary literature review, shedding light on the ongoing research directions. We have explored the essence and characteristics of AiArt, as these form the fundamental and vital aspects of this new art genre. By providing AiArt with a

label, we can define its nature and distinguish it from other art forms. We assert that the nature of AiArt is shaped by three key aspects: a diverse range of creative subjects, an intelligent creative medium, and a modern expression of meaning. Furthermore, we have summarized the fundamental characteristics of AiArt, extending from the present to the future, which encompass synesthesia experience, fluidity and adaptability, interaction and communication, as well as permeation and integration. Moving forward, we aspire to make progress through trial and error in exploring the theoretical foundations, models, and tools necessary to delve deeper into the potential of AiArt.

References

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